

Modelling of Bit Error Rate as a Function of Knife Edge Diffraction Loss Based on Line of Sight Percentage Clearance

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Abstract

In this paper, modelling of bit error rate as function of knife edge diffraction loss based on line of sight (LoS) percentage clearance is presented. Mathematical expressions for investigating the effect of variations in percentage clearance (C_p %) of 1st Fresnel zone on diffraction loss, bit energy per noise-density (E_b/N_0) in dB and bit error rate (BER) are presented. Also, the average error bits per second for binary phase shift keying (BPSK), pulse amplitude modulation (PAM) and 4-quadrature amplitude modulation (4-QAM) digital modulations in additive white-Gaussian-noise (AWGN) are specified. Simulated result is shown to analyse and compare the bit error rate as a function of diffraction loss for the selected digital modulation schemes. The results show that the reduction in percentage clearance for first Fresnel zone reduces the energy per noise-density thereby increasing bit error rate. MAT LAB results show that the average error bit per second of BPSK has 0.0000, PAM has 0.1429, and 4-QAM has 0.0009. In all, for any given percentage clearance, BPSK has the smallest number of error bits per second. Also, the lowest BER and the lowest number of error bits per second occur at about 70 % clearance of 1st Fresnel zone. For any given amount of reduction in C_p %, the corresponding increase in BER and number of error bits per second increases as data rate increases.

Keywords: Bit error rate, bit energy per noise-density, digital modulations, diffraction loss, Fresnel zone, diffraction parameter, percentage clearance.

1. Introduction

Diffraction is the bending of radio waves around obstacles in the path of the waves, or as the radio waves pass through narrow openings (Davies, 2014 & Qureshi et al., 2015). Diffraction occurs when a wave encounters an object in its path or when the wave is forced through a small opening. The loss that occurs due to the obstacle in the path of the signal is known as “diffraction loss” (Kumar, 2015). The concept of diffraction is explained by the Huygens-Fresnel principle which states that each point on a wave front acts as a point source (Tyson, 2012 & Tang et al., 2015).

This means that even if the direct path between the transmitter and receiver is blocked, some energy can reach the receiver from the portions of space that are visible to both the transmitter and receiver. Presently, determination of single knife edge diffraction loss requires the computation of obstruction clearance height, radius of the Fresnel zone and the diffraction loss. The several steps or levels of computations required can be significantly reduced if the percentage clearance is used rather than the clearance height. Also, determination of the diffraction parameters for different values of percentage clearance and frequency can be simplified by using percentage clearance scaling factor and frequency scaling. In order to estimate the losses caused by an obstacle in the signal path, it is usually assumed that the obstacle is a single knife-edge of negligible thickness or a thick smooth obstacle with a well-defined radius of curvature at the top (Galvez, 2010 & Argota et al).

Diffraction allows radio signals to propagate around the curved surface of the earth, beyond the horizon, and to propagate behind obstructions. Diffraction results in a change of direction of path of the radio wave energy from the normal line-of-sight path. Diffraction loss is a function of frequency of operation and the path geometry. If the direct line-of-sight of a radio wave or wireless signal is obstructed by a single object, such as a mountain or building, the attenuation resulting from diffraction over such obstacle can be determined by considering the obstacle as a single knife-edge (Qing, 2015). The Fresnel zone in this case defines the cylindrical ellipsoidal path actually occupied by the signal as it propagates from the transmitter to the receiver. Fresnel zones are numbered starting from one and there is infinite number of Fresnel zones. The more the number of Fresnel zones obstructed, the higher the diffraction loss due to the obstruction. However, only the first Fresnel zones have any real effect on radio propagation.

Excessive obstruction of the signal path can cause excess diffraction loss which can affect the system performance and quality of service. In the case of digital communication system, the excess diffraction loss can affect the bit energy per noise-density (E_b/N_o) and bit error rate (BER) Meanwhile, the BER probability varies with the specific digital modulation techniques employed (Sharma, 2010).

Consequently, in this paper, Modelling of bit error rate as a function of knife edge diffraction loss based on line of sight percentage clearance are studied for Binary Phase shift keying (BPSK), Pulse amplitude modulation (PAM) and 4- Quadrature amplitude modulation (4-QAM) digital modulations in additive white Gaussian-noise (AWGN). Also, the average error bits

per second (AVEBPS) versus percentage clearance of the first Fresnel zone are considered for the selected digital modulation schemes.

2.1 Bit Energy per Noise-Density

Bit energy or energy per bit in dBW represented as E_b is related to the total received power as;

$$E_b = P_{RX} - 10 \log(R_{bps}) \quad (1)$$

Where P_{RX} is the total received power in dBW and R_{bps} is data Rate or bit rate in bits per second.

Noise power density (N_o) in dBW is the thermal noise level of a perfect receiver in Hz and it is given as;

$$N_o = -204 + NF_{dB} \quad (2)$$

Where NF_{dB} is noise figure in dB.

Then, the bit energy per noise-density ($\frac{E_b}{N_o}$) is given as (Sklar, 2001);

$$\frac{E_b}{N_o} = P_{RX} - 10 \log(R_{bps}) + 204 - NF_{dB} \quad (3)$$

The total received power in dBW becomes;

$$P_{RX} = P_{TX} + G_{TXA} + G_{RXA} - L_{TX} - L_{RX} - L_{FSL} - L_{oL} - FM \quad (4)$$

Where P_{TX} is the transmitter power measured in dBW, and represents the power output of the transmitter at the waveguide flange; G_{TXA} is the transmitter antenna gain measured in dBi; G_{RXA} is the receiver antenna gain measured in dBi; L_{TX} is the transmitter losses include all components in transmit chain in dB; L_{RX} is the Receiver losses include all components in receiver chain in dB; L_{FSL} is the free-space loss in dB; L_{oL} is the sum of all other path losses (in dB) excluding the L_{FSL} , L_{TX} and L_{RX} . It includes losses like diffraction loss; FM is the fade margin in dB.

The free-space loss (L_{FSL}) in dB is given as;

$$L_{FSL} = 92.4 + 20 \log (f) + 20 \log (d) \tag{5}$$

Where f is the transmitted frequency in GHz and d is path length in km.

In this paper the effect of single knife edge diffraction loss is study. Hence, in this paper, the L_{OL} is assumed to be a single knife edge diffraction loss designated as L_{DFL} . Therefore,

$$P_{RX} = P_{TX} + G_{TXA} + G_{RXA} - L_{TX} - L_{RX} - L_{FSL} - L_{DFL} - FM \tag{6}$$

$$\frac{E_b}{N_o} = P_{TX} + G_{TXA} + G_{RXA} - L_{TX} - L_{RX} - L_{FSL} - L_{DFL} - FM - 10 \log (R_{bps}) + 204 - NF_{dB} \tag{7}$$

2.2 Diffraction Loss as a Function of Diffraction Parameters

Obstructions along the radio path leads to additional losses know as diffraction losses. When the obstruction is a single obstacle between the transmitter and receiver, then it can be modelled by a single knife edge diffraction loss (Blaunstein & Christodoulou, 2014). Lee’s approximation for single knife edge diffraction loss, L_{DFL} (in dB) as a function of the Fresnel-Kirchoff diffraction parameter, $V_{(x)}$ at distance of x from the transmitter is given as follows (Baldassaro, 2001):

$$LDFL = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} 0 & \text{for } V_{(x)} < -1 \\ 20\log (0.5 - 0.62V_{(x)}) & \text{for } -1 \leq V_{(x)} \leq 0 \\ 20\log (0.5\exp(-0.95V_{(x)})) & \text{for } 0 \leq V_{(x)} \leq 1 \\ 20\log \left(0.4 - \sqrt{0.1184 - (0.38 - 0.1V_{(x)})^2} \right) & \text{for } 1 \leq V_{(x)} \leq 2.4 \\ 20\log \left(\frac{0.225}{V_{(x)}} \right) & \text{for } V_{(x)} > 2.4 \end{array} \right\} \tag{8}$$

The Fresnel-Kirchoff diffraction parameter ($V_{(x)}$) at any given distance x between the transmitter and the receiver is given as (Malila et al., 2015; Hector et al., 2015; Lambrechts et al., 2015; & Bhuvaneshs et al., 2015).

$$V_{(x)} = h_{(x)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{2(d_{t(x)} + d_{r(x)})}{\lambda(d_{t(x)})(d_{r(x)})}} \right) \quad (9)$$

Where $d_{t(x)}$ is the distance of location x from the transmitter; and $d_{r(x)}$ is the distance of location x from the receiver, where $x = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$.

$$d_{t(x)} + d_{r(x)} = d \quad (10)$$

d is the total distance between the transmitter and the receiver.

The effective obstruction height $h(x)$ which is the height (in metres) is the height from the tip of the obstruction at location x to a point on the line of sight at location x , where x is between the transmitter and the receiver.

The wavelength λ of the radio wave in metres where;

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{f} \quad (11)$$

Where, c is the speed of a radio wave ($c = 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$); and f is frequency of the radio wave in Hz. For LoS links, the radius of the n th Fresnel zone ($r_{(n)}$) is given as (Ahamed & Faruque, 2015; Sun & Bancroft, 2002; Wang et al., 2016; Koplov et al., 1996; Jouad et al., 2016).

$$r_{(n)} = \sqrt{\frac{n\{\lambda(d_{t(x)})(d_{r(x)})\}}{(d_{t(x)} + d_{r(x)})}} \quad (12)$$

2.3 Diffraction Parameter for Any Percentage Clearance of Fresnel Zone

Let $Cp_{(x,n)}$ be the percentage clearance required for Fresnel zone n . In practice, at least 60% of $r_{(1)}$ (that is, 0.6 of $r_{(1)}$) clearance is required for the first Fresnel zone. $Cp_{(x,n)}$ Clearance for $r_{(n)}$ translates to effective obstruction height $h_{(x,CP)}$ given as;

$$h_{(x,CP)} = \frac{Cp_{(x,n)}}{100} (-r_{(n)}) = \left(\frac{Cp_{(x,n)}}{100} \right) \left(\sqrt{\frac{n\{\lambda(d_{t(x)})(d_{r(x)})\}}{(d_{t(x)} + d_{r(x)})}} \right) \quad (13)$$

Where $Cp_{(x,n)} > 0\%$ (i.e. positive) if the obstruction height is below the LoS; $Cp_{(x,n)} = 0\%$ if the obstruction height is on the LoS; and $Cp_{(x,n)} < 0\%$ (i.e. negative) if the obstruction height is above the LoS.

$$\text{Hence, for } Cp_{(x,n)} = 60\%, h_{(x,60)} = 0.6(-r_{(n)})$$

In terms of $Cp_{(x,n)}$, the Fresnel-Kirchhoff diffraction parameter at any given location x between the transmitter and the receiver can be represented as $(V_{(x,CP)})$ and it is given as;

$$V_{(x,CP)} = h_{(x,CP)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{2(d_t(x) + d_r(x))}{\lambda(d_t(x))(d_r(x))}} \right) \tag{14}$$

$$V_{(x,CP)} = - \left(\frac{Cp_{(x,n)}}{100} \right) (\sqrt{2n}) \tag{15}$$

Lee's approximation for single knife edge diffraction loss, $G_d(\text{dB})$ as a function of $V_{(x,CP)}$ is given as;

$$L_{DFL} = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} 0 & \text{for } V_{(x,CP)} < -1 \\ 20\log(0.5 - 0.62V_{(x,CP)}) & \text{for } -1 \leq V_{(x,CP)} \leq 0 \\ 20\log(0.5\exp(-0.95V_{(x,CP)})) & \text{for } 0 \leq V_{(x,CP)} \leq 1 \\ 20\log\left(0.4 - \sqrt{0.1184 - (0.38 - 0.1V_{(x,CP)})^2}\right) & \text{for } 1 \leq V_{(x,CP)} \leq 2.4 \\ 20\log\left(\frac{0.225}{V_{(x,CP)}}\right) & \text{for } V_{(x,CP)} > 2.4 \end{array} \right\} \tag{16}$$

2.4 Bit Error Rate of the Selected Digital Modulation Schemes

Bit Error Rate (BER) is the number of bit errors that occur for a given number of bits transmitted. It is related to the error probability because it is the ratio of bit errors to bits transmitted (Beasley & Miller, 2007). The energy per bit is the amount of power in a digital bit for a given amount of time. Bit error rate can be expressed as follows;

$$\text{BER} = \frac{\text{Number of Errors Bits}}{\text{Total Number of Bits Sent}} \tag{17}$$

$$\text{Number of ErrorBits} = \text{BER} \times \text{Total Number of Bits Sent} \quad (18)$$

For example, a transmission might have an if BER of 10^{-6} meaning that, out of every 1,000,000 bits transmitted, one bit was in error. Also, in terms of bit rate, BER can be expressed as;

$$\text{BER} = \frac{\text{Average Bits Error Per Second}}{\text{Bit Rate}} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{Average Bits Error Per Second} = \text{BER} \times \text{Bit Rate} \quad (20)$$

For instance, if $\text{BER} = 10^{-4}$ and Bit rate = 1Mbps then average bits error per second = $10^{-4} \times 1\text{Mbps} = 10^{-4} \times 1 \times 10^6 = 1 \times 10^2 = 100$ error bits per second.

The bit error probability is the expectation value of the BER. The BER can be considered as an approximate estimate of the bit error probability. The BER, as a measure of the signal quality is a function of the bit energy per noise-density (E_b/N_o) of the signal. Usually, E_b/N_o is used to compare two or more digital modulation techniques that uses different transmission rate. The values of BER in terms of E_b/N_o in an AWGN channel are expressed differently for the different digital modulation schemes (Mongre & Kpoor, 2013). For Binary Phase Shift Keying Modulation (BPSK) modulation in additive white-Gaussian-noise (AWGN) the theoretical Bit Error Rate (BER) can be calculated with respect to $\frac{E_b}{N_o}$ as follows (Rahaman, 2013; Dhabhai, 2014; Pillar, 2008 & Dixit DuttBohra, 2014).

$$\text{BER}_{(\text{BPSK})} = \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_b}{N_o}} \right) \quad (21)$$

Where $\text{erfc}(x) = 1 - \text{erf}(x)$ and $\text{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^x e^{-t^2} dt$

For Pulse Amplitude Modulation (4-PAM) modulation in an AWGN channel, the theoretical BER is given by (Rahaman, 2013; & Pillar, 2008);

$$\text{BER}_{(4\text{PAM})} = \frac{3}{4} \text{erfc} \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_b}{5(N_o)}} \right) \quad (22)$$

For 4 Point Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (4-QAM) modulations in an AWGN channel, the theoretical BER is given by (Rahaman, 2013; & Pillar, 2008);

$$\text{BER}_{(4\text{QAM})} = \text{erfc}\left(\frac{E_b}{2(N_o)}\right) \quad (23)$$

3. The Simulation Process

This dissertation is based on analytical modelling and simulation; there is no empirical implementation. The path profile data are derived from online path profile software, which is obtained using satellite imagery of the case study site, they are not empirically measured. Ideally, locally measured data would be better, but there is no such data. So, the result accuracy depends on data used. The analytical modelling is based on link budget parameters for LoS microwave frequency.

First, based on the analytical expressions in the preceding section, a sample computation is done with diffraction loss of 0dB, data rate of 150 Mbps, and with the following C-band microwave link specifications; $P_{\text{TX}} = 10$ dBW, $G_{\text{TXA}} = 30$ dBi, $G_{\text{RXA}} = 30$ dBi, $L_{\text{TX}} = 3.08$ dB, $L_{\text{RX}} = 3.08$ dB, $NF_{\text{dB}} = 8$ dB, $f = 3.0$ GHz, $d = 40$ km, $FM = 20$ dB, $R_{\text{bps}} = 150$ Mbps and $L_{\text{oL}} = L_{\text{DFL}} = 0$ dB frequencies band and with other communication parameters for the link budget equations.

Secondly, the effect of diffraction loss on the error performance of digital wireless, the BER and average bits error per second are evaluated for different digital modulation schemes and at different percentage clearance ($C_{p(x,n)}$) of the Fresnel zone are conducted for $-100\% \leq C_{p(x,n)} \leq 100\%$ and for different Data Rates of 1 Mbps. Notably, different percentage clearance of the Fresnel zone give different diffraction loss and hence, affect the bit energy per noise-density ($\frac{E_b}{N_o}$) and the corresponding bit error rate (BER). The modulation schemes considered in the simulation are;

- i. Binary Phase Shift Keying Modulation (BPSK) modulation
- ii. Pulse Amplitude Modulation (4-PAM) modulation
- iii. 4 Point Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (4-QAM)

The theoretical BER versus $\frac{E_b}{N_o}$ for each of the three digital modulations techniques are obtained. In plotting the graph of BER versus $\frac{E_b}{N_o}$, the log-linear type of semi-log graph scale is used. The log-linear type of semi-log graph is defined by a logarithmic scale on the y-axis, and a linear scale on the x-axis. Hence, in plotting the graph of BER versus $\frac{E_b}{N_o}$, the values of $\frac{E_b}{N_o}$ used are in the linear scale. So, $\frac{E_b}{N_o}$ in dB converts to $10\left(\left(\frac{E_b}{N_o}\right)/10\right)$ in the linear scale while the logarithmic scale of BER converts to $\log_{10}(\text{BER})$ in the logarithmic scale. Thus, $\left[\frac{E_b}{N_o}\right]_{\text{linear}} = 10\left(\left(\frac{E_b}{N_o}\right)/10\right)$ and $[\text{BER}]_{\log} = \log_{10}(\text{BER})$. So, the semi-log version of the BER for each of the three modulation techniques becomes;

$$[\text{BER}_{(\text{BPSK})}]_{\log} = \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(\sqrt{\left[\frac{E_b}{N_o}\right]_{\text{linear}}} \right) \quad (24)$$

$$[\text{BER}_{(4\text{PAM})}]_{\log} = \frac{3}{4} \text{erfc} \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{5} \left[\frac{E_b}{N_o}\right]_{\text{linear}}} \right) \quad (25)$$

$$[\text{BER}_{(4\text{QAM})}]_{\log} = \text{erfc} \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{E_b}{N_o}\right]_{\text{linear}}} \right) \quad (26)$$

4. Results and Discussion

The results of the sample computation are as follows; $L_{\text{FSL}} = 92.4 + 20 \log (3.0) + 20 \log (40) = 133.984 \text{ dB}$

$$P_{\text{RX}} = 10 + 30 + 30 - 3.08 - 3.08 - 133.984 - 0 - 20 = -90.144 \text{ dB}$$

$$\frac{E_b}{N_o} = -90.144 - 10 \log (150 \times 10^6) + 204 - 8 = 24.0955 \text{ dB}$$

$$\text{BER}_{(\text{BPSK})} = \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc}(\sqrt{24.0955}) = 1.933 \times 10^{-12}$$

$$BER_{(BQAM)} = \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{24.0955}{2}\right)}\right) = 9.1674 \times 10^{-7}$$

$$BER_{(BAM)} = \frac{3}{4} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{24.0955}{5}\right)}\right) = 0.0014$$

The second set of results is for simulations conducted for $-100\% \leq C_{p(x,n)} \leq 100\%$ and for different Data Rates of 1 Mbps.

Table 1: Variation of diffraction parameter (V), diffraction loss in dB and bit energy per noise-density ($\frac{E_b}{N_0}$) In dB with percentage clearance (Cp (%)) of the 1st Fresnel Zone

Percentage Clearance Cp (%)	Diffraction Loss (dB)	Eb/No (dB)
100	0	24.0955
80	0	24.0955
60	0.2237	24.3191
40	-1.4042	22.6912
20	-3.4093	20.6862
0	-6.0206	18.0749
-20	-7.8172	16.2783
-40	-10.9778	13.1177
-60	-13.0294	11.0661
-80	-14.7614	9.3341
-100	-16.3604	7.7351

Figure 1: Diffraction loss versus percentage clearance of the 1st Fresnel zone at 150 Mbps.

Table 1 and Figures 1 show that the diffraction loss is zero for $80\% \leq$ percentage clearance (C_p) $< 100\%$ but it increased above zero at 0.2237 for $60\% \leq C_p \leq 80\%$. For all $C_p < 60\%$ the diffraction loss falls as percentage clearance falls.

Figure 2: Bit energy per noise-density versus percentage clearance of the 1st Fresnel zone at 150 Mbps.

Table 1 and Figures 2 shows that, the energy per noise density in (dB) is constant for $80\% \leq$ percentage clearance (C_p) $\leq 100\%$ but it increased with a value of 24.3191 for $60\% \leq C_p \leq 80\%$. The reduction in the C_p (%) reduces the energy per noise density in dB.

Table 2: BER (dB) versus percentage clearance (C_p (%)) of the 1st Fresnel zone for the three digital modulations techniques at data rates of 150 Mbps.

E_b/N_0 (dB)	Percentage Clearance C_p (%)	Diffraction Loss (dB)	Log of BER BPSK (dB)	Log of BER PAM (dB)	Log of BER QAM (dB)	Diffraction parameter V_x (dB)
24.0955	100	0	-11.7137	-2.8449	-6.0377	-1.4142
24.0955	80	0	-11.7137	-2.8449	-6.0377	-1.1314
24.3191	60	0.2237	-11.8128	-2.8660	-6.0882	-0.8485
22.6912	40	-1.4042	-11.0913	-2.7118	-5.7207	-0.5657
20.6862	20	-3.4093	-10.2013	-2.5206	-5.2668	-0.2828
18.0749	0	-6.0206	-9.0392	-2.2694	-4.6729	0
16.2783	-20	-7.8172	-8.2374	-2.0948	-4.2621	0.2828
13.1177	-40	-10.9778	-6.8207	-1.7828	-3.5338	0.5657
11.0661	-60	-13.0294	-5.8953	-1.5761	-3.0559	0.8485
9.3341	-80	-14.7614	-5.1091	-1.3980	-2.6479	1.1314
7.7351	-100	-16.3604	-4.3777	-1.2296	-2.2663	1.4142

Figure 6: Modulation techniques versus bit energy per noise-density at 150 Mbps.

Table 2 and Figure 6 show the comparison of the three digital modulation schemes. BER in BPSK has -11.8128, BER in PAM has -28660 and BER in 4-QAM has -6.0882 for 60 % < Cp < 80%. The results show that BER in BPSK has the smallest number of bit error rate while BER in 4-QAM has the highest number of bit error rate.

Figure 7: Diffraction loss with bit energy per noise-density versus percentage clearance of the 1st Fresnel zone at 150 Mbps.

Figure 8: BER versus percentage clearance of the 1st Fresnel zone at 150 Mbps (S-band).

In Table 2, Figure 7 and Figure 8, shows that, the BER is not affected by for $80\% \leq C_p (\%) \leq 100\%$ since the diffraction loss is zero in this region. However, BER decreased for $60\% \leq C_p (\%) < 80\%$ and then for all percentage clearance $C_p (\%) < 60\%$ the BER increases as percentage clearance $C_p (\%)$ decreases.

Table 3: Average errors bits per second (AVEBPS) versus percentage clearance of the 1st Fresnel zone for the three digital modulation techniques at 1Mbps

Percentage Clearance(%)	BER BPSK (dB)	BER PAM (dB)	BER 4QAM (dB)
100	0.0000	0.1429	0.0009
80	0.0000	0.1429	0.0009
60	0.0000	0.1361	0.0008
40	0.0000	0.1942	0.0019
20	0.0001	0.3015	0.0054
0	0.0009	0.5377	0.0212
-20	0.0058	0.8039	0.0547
-40	0.1511	1.6488	0.2925
-60	1.2726	2.6540	0.8792
-80	7.7780	3.9996	2.2493
-100	41.9094	5.8935	5.4158

Figure 9: Average error bits per second versus percentage clearance of the 1st Fresnel zone for the three digital modulation techniques at 1 Mbps

Table 3 and Figure 9 shows that the BPSK has 0.0000 error bits per second at CP% = 100% whereas 4-QAM and 4-PAM have 0.1429 and 0.0009 error bits per second respectively. The error bits per second reduced at 60 % clearance. The average change in error bit per second is computed with respect to the BER at CP% = 100%. However, for all Cp (%) < 60 % the number of error bits per second increased for all the three modulation schemes. In all, for any given Cp (%), the BPSK has the smallest number of error bits per second while PAM has the highest number of error bits per second. In essence, the higher the data rate, the higher the impact of changes in Cp (%) on number of error bits per second.

5. Conclusion

The modelling of bit error rate as a function of knife edge diffraction loss based on line of sight percentage clearance was examined. Particularly, the results of the mathematical expressions for examining the variations of the diffraction parameter, diffraction loss, bit energy per noise-density E_b/N_0 in dB and bit error rate (BER) with percentage clearance of 1st Fresnel zone are presented. The paper considered three different digital modulations in additive white-Gaussian-noise. The modulation schemes considered are Binary phase shift keying modulation, Pulse amplitude modulation and 4-Point quadrature amplitude modulation. The results show that the reduction in percentage clearance of 1st Fresnel zone reduces the bit energy per noise-density thereby increasing the BER. For each of the modulation schemes, the

actual number of error bits per second is determined for any given percentage clearance of 1st Fresnel zone. The results of the mathematical expressions presented in this paper are useful for digital wireless network planners and designers to ensure that the selected parameters will not violate the specified error performance when subjected to variations in the available diffraction loss in the communication link.

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